

Biospheric functions of humic substances – geochemical barriers and nature-like technologies

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A key function of humic substances is their ability to reduce the migration of toxic water components. Lake waters and soil waters in the protected area of the Novgorod Region contain varying proportions of natural organic matter, and, accordingly, geochemical barriers also vary in their retention strength.

The concentration of allochthonous organic matter (flows from the catchment area) and autochthonous organic matter (formed within the reservoir) in lake waters varies depending on temperature, which affects the balance of accessible and labile metal species.

The greatest influence of autochthonous organic matter on metal formation, over a time scale, is characteristic of the alkaline Lake Valdaiskoye in virtually all periods. This influence is greatest during the growing season (summer) and the period of maximum phytoplankton destruction (fall) and the release of organic matter. In summer, 70% of the total organic matter in the water is autochthonous, and in autumn, up to 60%. The contribution of autochthonous matter to metal complexation in waters from lysimetric ponds located near the city is somewhat lower. The main metals associated with such organic compounds are copper, zinc,

The waters of the acidified Lake Gusinoe are characterized by a dominant content of humic acids in organic matter (up to 90%, even in summer); the most stable complex compounds are formed with iron, aluminum, copper, and nickel ions. Lysimetric waters in the forest zone in spring and summer contain up to 40% complex compounds of metals with lower molecular weight organic matter. As in the corresponding lake, cationic compounds with humic polymers predominate.

Changes in zeta potential directly depend on the balance of allochthonous and autochthonous components. Lysimetric waters of the humus horizon in forests, with very low pH and zero alkalinity, generate a significant electrochemically negative potential, characteristic of stable organic colloids, primarily of humic origin. An increase in the content of autochthonous organic matter shifts this potential toward zero and positive values, so not all ratios of allochthonous and autochthonous substances in natural waters are thermodynamically stable.

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